

during both wet and dry seasons, but dry season rates were only about 50% of those in the wet season. This may be due to a rise in groundwater table during the monsoon period. Initial concentrations of ammoniacal and nitrate N were high, gradually dropping within 15 d after application of N (see table). N loss increased with increasing water depth. N loss in the dry season was about 50% of loss in the wet season. □

Effect of submergence depth on rice yield and loss of water and N.^a Thanjavur, India, 1985-87 wet and dry seasons.

Water depth (cm)	Wet season				Dry season			
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water loss (mm)	N loss (kg/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)	Water loss (mm)	N loss (kg/ha)	
			NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻			NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻
2.5	6.4	373	4.6	1.3	4.6	196	2.2	0.6
5.0	6.6	448	5.5	1.6	4.7	238	2.7	0.8
7.5	6.2	516	6.2	1.8	4.4	265	3.0	0.9
LSD (0.05)	ns				0.1			

^aAv for 3 yr.

Effect of irrigation schedule on grain yield and water use efficiency in transplanted rice

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Five levels of irrigation (see table) were laid out in randomized block design with four replications.

Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam, pH 6.8, EC 0.28 dS/m, 0.58% organic C, with 185, 18, and 250 kg available N, P, and K/ha. Test variety was IR36.

Water applied 1 or 3 d after

Effect of irrigation schedule on rice grain yield, water requirement, and water use efficiency. Ambikapur, India, 1987 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Effective rainfall (cm)	Water requirement (cm)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per cm)
Continuous submergence 5 ± 2 cm water (CS)	3.7	36	126	29
Application of 7 cm water 1 DAD	3.7	43	113	32
Application of 7 cm water 3 DAD	3.5	46	88	40
Application of 7 cm water 5 DAD	3.4	47	82	41
Rainfed with provision to store all rainwater (RF)	3.1	74	74	42
LSD (0.05)	0.2			

disappearance of ponded water (DAD) was as good as continuous submergence (CS) in grain yield and

significantly superior to rainfed (RF). Irrigation 3 DAD saved 38 cm water without sacrificing yield. □

Farm machinery

A root zone liquid urea applicator for wetland rice

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A simple root zone liquid applicator attachment to the hand compression insecticide sprayer was developed in 1984 (see figure). Prilled urea dissolved in water (1:2 ratio) is kept under pressure in the sprayer tank. The applicator is attached in place of the insecticide lance rod using an adaptor pipe with matching threads.

The operator lifts the applicator with the right hand and gently pushes the lower ends of eight branch nozzles

Urea solution application using root zone liquid applicator attachment to hand compression sprayer. AP, India, 1984-1986.

5 to 10 cm deep into the root zone in water-saturated soil. The trigger is pressed with the left hand for 1-2 s to release the urea solution. An area of about 0.63 m² is covered with each release, a volume of 250-450 liters/ha. Two to three labor days are required to cover a hectare.

We evaluated the applicator in black clayey soil for four seasons 1984-86.

In wet season Jun-Dec 1984, 60 kg N/ha applied using the applicator at 10 d after transplanting (DT) gave a yield of 5.2 t/ha comparable to 5.4 t/ha with urea supergranule (USG) placement.

These yields were significantly better than with split application (4.7 t/ha).

In dry season Jan-Apr 1985, the three fertilizer forms were compared at 80 kg N/ha in row and random transplanted rice. Urea solution and USG in the applied root zone produced grain yields (5.6-5.75 t/ha) significantly better than that with best split broadcast (5.3 t/ha).

In wet season 1985, urea solution at 88 kg N/ha applied in the root zone gave a significantly higher yield (4.3 t/ha) than best split broadcast (4.09 t/ha).

We also evaluated the applicator for insecticide application in the root zone (see table). Root zone application of carbofuran suspension (RACS) and three granular broadcasts of carbofuran (TGBC) were significantly better than single granular broadcast of carbofuran (SGBC) in controlling stem borer and whorl maggot (*Hydrellia* sp.). The yield increase with RACS was 1.5 t/ha. The benefit:cost ratio was 5.45 with RACS.

The applicator can be used without modification in both row- and randomly transplanted rice. □

Effect of root zone placement and granular broadcast of carbofuran on pest incidence and grain yields.^a AP, India, 1984-86.

Treatment ^b	Whorl maggot (ADL/hill) 46 DT, 1986 DS	Stem borer			Grain yield ^c (t/ha)				Increase		Cost of control (US\$/ha)		BC ^e ratio
		Deadhearts (%) 60 DT, 1985 DS	Deadhearts (%) 49 DT, 1985 WS	Whiteheads (%) 1984 WS	1984 WS	1985 DS	1986 DS	Mean	Yield (t/ha)	Income (US\$/ha)	Labor	Insecticide ^d	
Carbofuran 50 SP suspension applied 15 DT (RACS)	1.05 a	1.05 a	1.9 a	3.42 b	5.7 a	6.2 ab	4.1 a	5.3	1.5	191	3	32	5.45
Hand placement of carbofuran 3G-impregnated mud-balls at 15 DT	—	1.76 a	1.7 a	0.76 a	5.7 a	6.1 b	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Carbofuran 3G broadcast at 15 DT (SGBC)	5.75 b	3.02 b	7.2 b	4.29 b	5.1 b	5.8 b	2.2 b	4.4	0.5	68.4	0.5	41.7	1.62
Carbofuran 3G broadcast at 15, 35, 55 DT (TGBC)	4.69 b	1.06 a	7.7 b	4.03 b	5.7 a	6.9 a	4.0 a	5.5	1.7	212.8	1.5	125	1.68
Untreated control	11.37 c	10.9 c	17.0 c	11.5 c	4.6 c	5.1 c	1.8 c	3.8	—	—	—	—	—

^aIn each column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at $p = 0.05$ by LSD. ^bCarbofuran was applied @0.75 kg ai/ha per application. ^cGrain yield data of 1985 WS were excluded because rice tungro virus caused very low yields. ^dCarbofuran 50 SP (soluble powder) was about 30% cheaper than 3G. ^eIncremental benefit-to-cost ratio = additional returns/additional cost. DT = days after transplanting, ADL = average damaged leaves, DS = dry season (Jan-Apr), WS = wet season (Jun-Dec). — = treatment not tested.

Farming systems

Economics of rainfed rice-based crop sequences under upland conditions in the Lower Brahmaputra Valley

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We evaluated seven rice-based

cropping sequences 1985-86 to 1986-87. Local rice variety Banglami was grown Mar-Jun followed by black gram or sesamum Jun-Aug and wheat, buckwheat, mustard, niger, or potato Nov-Feb.

Soil of the test site was sandy loam. Rice received 20-10-10 kg NPK/ha and yielded 0.97-1.01 t/ha. (Yields were reduced because of pest infestation.) Black gram and sesamum received 15-35-10 and 30-20-20 kg

NPK/ha, respectively. Black gram yielded from 0.34-0.59 t/ha; sesamum, 0.63-0.79 t/ha.

Sonalika wheat received 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha; buckwheat and niger 20-10-10; M27 mustard 40-35-15, and lalbahari potato 60-50-50. Net return was calculated for each crop and cropping sequence.

Rice - black gram - potato gave the highest net return, followed by rice - sesamum - potato. Net return per day